

THE ROLE OF TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT (TQM) IN ENHANCEMENT MANAGEMENT QUALITY EDUCATIONAL SERVICES : STUDY CASE OF SMAN 1 PURWANTORO

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ABSTRACT

Education is very important for life, especially today. Education is the mandate of independence. The field of education always makes improvements from time to time to realize the ideal conditions of fair and equitable education. One of the improvements made can be using the Total Quality Management (TQM) technique. TQM is an approach to improve the quality of management and service. SMAN 1 Purwanto is one of the schools that uses TQM as a method to improve school competence. This study aims to see how the role of TQM in improving the quality of service and the quality of education in SMAN 1 Purwanto. This research is descriptive qualitative research with a field observation approach and literature study. The data used are primary data with as many as 7 sources obtained through observation for 1 semester and interviews. The results showed that the application of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwanto had a role in increasing the achievements of SMAN 1 Purwanto in various fields. Achievement is also evenly distributed among educators or students or schools in general. The application of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwanto is in accordance with the TQM concept so that the results obtained are also in accordance with what is expected.

Keywords : TQM, Management, Quality, Service, School,

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is very important aspect for life every nation. Education is mandate independence because education is track main for increase intelligence and open various opportunity as well as opportunity for every individual for could get decent life. Education is recognized worldwide as a something holding aspect role important in life people human. One size progress something nation based on how much Up education achieved by the nation (Priarni, 2017).

Innovation in education Keep going continuously developed to achieve something ideal condition of education which accepted by all. Improvement after improvement Keep going done so that education could give continuous science develop in accordance with demands of the times and development knowledge. Opportunity more work many develop with a variety of modern work models of course demand knowledge and skills acquired in school also developed and adapted. At this moment, the faster development technology, demands more skills which must have controlled by individuals. The skills requirement in the present and the past are different. because of it, repair and improvement condition education must keep going done.

Challenges faced by humans in the era of industrialization characterize rich information and attitude study lifetime alive, rational thinking, have creativity on new challenge, have ability to anticipation, innovation, and responsibility (Hasanah, 2013). regarding with Thing that, need existence management knowledge which is management to asset knowledge and organization

for create a value that can be fulfill demands tactical and strategic (Chandorkar, 2021). Management enhancement quality school is one thing already should do. Management enhancement quality integrated or often called with Total Quality Management (TQM) is one of the draft management enhancement expected quality could give influence significant to improvement of education (Indana, 2017) and already applied in Indonesia (Fahrudin, 2020).

School State Senior High School (SMAN) 1 Purwantoro is one schools that use TQM in effort enhancement quality service school. TQM just not give changes to the system operational school but also balance quality education between student and it is a vital advantage in development system education (Basbas, 2022). There is not only vision mision school and motto, SMAN 1 Purwantoro by special have a service motto namely "Prime in Service, Forward in Education". That thing is reflection that party school with aware confess that success an educational process could not release from role of quality services provided by the school.

Facilities at SMAN 1 Purwantoro keep going developed and improved good facility by physique nor non-physical facilities. Facility physique cover procurement extracurricular buildings and arenas. Non-physical facilities cover system service, system education and teaching, as well as system security, and so on. SMAN 1 Purwantoro Keep going strive for could give appropriate education with development of the times. The effort just not be spoken but also in harmony with actions taken by the party's school. Is effort party school in increase quality service education with apply Total Quality Management (TQM) has impact to quality service at SMAN 1 Purwantoro?

Related with that, this research has destination for see and study about impact the application of TQM to quality service education at SMAN 1 Purwantoro. Allegedly that TQM has role in enhancement quality services at SMAN 1 Purwantoro. This study expected could give benefit for public especially in the world of education. Existence study this expected could give description about technical and concept enhancement quality service education through TQM. By general, research about TQM already many found however this study take locus which one is new yet once held study kind around area location research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

TQM is something approach in effort for increase power competitive organization at the level as much as possible through improvements made to various thing in organization like improvements to products, services, human resources, systems, and the environment around. It is also stated that what is meant by with TQM is effort keep going coordinated continuous with good purpose for repair quality services provided to customer. Customers in education of course is student.

The three most famous conception of quality developed by three expert quality best level international namely W. Edwards Deming, Philip B. Crosby, and Joseph M. Juran (Jasuri, 2017). According to Deming quality is all something the customer wants and needs. Crosby explained that quality is level suitability something with specified conditions. Juran mention

that what is meant with quality according to herself is suitability something with standard specs on something that.

Management enhancement quality naturally is part from knowledge management. Management itself could interpreted as a series of related processes with planning, organizing, executing, and controlling or evaluation (Zahroh, 2015). Design system management quality to achieve condition integrated quality and management quality at least cover principles, goals, curriculum, competence, professionalism, pattern teacher-student relationship, method learning, infrastructure, evaluation, and financing (Syarifah, 2020). The first TQM term appeared in the 1920s and beyond developed in Japan in the 1940s and continuously develop until this moment (Septiadi, 2019).

TQM has focus on the stages of the process and its achievement the goal already determines. Start with stage repair quality until Step TQM application thorough so that expected implementation of TQM can repair error in produce products that can be give satisfaction for customer. The main study of TQM can be interpreted through quality. Quality could describe as quality of management. If the quality presented by an organization no represent complete trust to customer, then existence organization for capable compete with other organizations will experience problematic.

According to Slamet in (Septiadi, 2019) draft the main TQM consists of of 5 things namely:

1. Customer focused.
2. There is systematic process improvement.
3. Future long thinking
4. There is development on human resources.
5. There is commitment from all element organization for maintain quality.

TQM must customer focused on the meaning of TQM is a system Which management is the focus is on fulfillment needs and wants from customer. because of that, every organization or the institution that means using TQM in enhancement quality must understand characteristics customer as well as could to do identify and perform analysis about what only what customers need and expect is in that organization or institution. Without understand characteristics needs and wants customer naturally TQM implementation will not effective because the wanted never to will could fulfilled.

Existence systematic process improvement could interpret as existence something the conditions under which each stage of the process already have good planning, executed by precise and thorough, and then to do evaluation to results that have been achieved. Systematic processes also refer to to suitability between work processes with desired achievement achieved. If results achieved not yet fulfill expected achievement so need conducted improvement and organization or institution related must with responsive to do repair. Repair must keep going conducted until obtained suitable result with the target.

TQM should also have nature is thinking period length that can be interpreted that TQM implementation must be in accordance with vision wanted mission achieved by the organization or deep institution study this is school. Vision and mission is leadman tree something organization that will keep going held and made as base in various things to be implemented by the organization. Vision is the statement in it contain a hope or the dream you want achieved by the that organization. As for the mission is steps or which stages taken by an organization in skeleton reach vision. Vision and mission are something in nature have long period. because of that, TQM which is based on the vision and mission must have thinking long period.

TQM concept is must there is development human resources. Executor management quality is man so existence enhancement quality service of course demand existence development human resources good by direct nor not straight away. Everyone involved in organization must have effort for could dominate competence in accordance with role duties and responsibilities carried out. On organization there must a transfer of knowledge and learning Among one member with other members. Meaning from this are all members could utilize all source study for increase competence of each member.

Last part from TQM concept is existence commitment from organization for maintain quality. Could interpreted that all members involved with organization must have awareness full and confident about importance quality or quality performance from member organization. Needed compactness member organization in skeleton maintain quality organization. Resistance quality no will could achieved if only implemented by several member. The effort for maintain standard quality certain. Therefore, commitment member organization and effort as well as effort every member in guard quality is important and fundamental thing because TQM is related with quality sustainable quality. _

3. IMPLEMENTATION METHOD

Study this is research using method qualitative descriptive. Study with method qualitative descriptive study with method qualitative descriptive is research that has destination for get results in depth research. On research qualitative results obtained no measurable by mathematical however have depth meaning obtained from respondent because nature study qualitative is emic no epic. It means all existing thing _ in study is must base on what is felt and stated by the respondent no just assumption from researcher sheer. Study Qualitative also emphasizes depth meaning no generalization (Yasin, 2021). Study it also uses approach studies literature to get about concept and understanding related Total Quality Management (TQM).

Data used in research this is primary data cause researcher To do data retrieval independent and not rely on the publication of data from party another. Data collection is done with method observations and interviews. Observation conducted for 1 semester or active period learning with a period of 5 months and 15 days. Research location is at SMAN 1 Purwantoro which is located on Jl. Raya Tegalrejo Purwantoro , Wonogiri , Central Java . Interview performed on several elements that have linkages with school such as teachers, employees school and participants educate . The sources who were interviewed in the research this consist of 7 people, namely:

1. 1 deputy head school field curriculum
2. 1 deputy head school field student
3. 1 administrative officer
4. 2 teachers
5. 2 students

Study qualitative started with to do data collection. Stages next after do data collection is data classification, data reduction, data verification, and stages final are data presentation. Data collection is all data obtained from the process of observation and interviews conducted by researchers. Stage data classification is stages group data accordingly with data characteristics. Data reduction is stages discard data or remove the data that is felt no need or no relevant with theme research. Stage next that is Step data verification done with to do check and do verification of the remaining data after Step reduction. Is there data really relevant and appropriate data with needs study or still mixed with other real data not enough relevant and not have linkages with research. Stage final is data presentation that is stages where the data that has been verified and confirmed suitability with theme study used for to do discussion in research. Based on a series of processes expected that the data used in discussion is true data that has relevance tall with destination research.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SMAN 1 Purwantoro was established in 1991 to be exact on May 5th. Moment This is SMAN 1 Purwantoro consist of 24 groups learning that consists of of 8 groups study in class X, 8 groups studying in class XI, and 8 groups study in class XII. SMAN 1 Purwantoro is one school adiwiyata with predicate A. SMAN 1 Purwantoro have vision “High achievement, strong character, insightful environment, empowered competitive, based on faith and piety”. Each of the components contained in vision have indicator. As for indicators of each component is as following:

- 1) Indicator high achievement. Based on deputy chief 's speech school field student indicator achievers high at SMAN 1 Purwantoro is increase interest and power competitive participant educate for could continue studies to college hig. This thing because no a little from participant educated at SMAN 1 Purwantoro more choose for direct plunge to the world of work compared to continue studies to college high . Indicator second is realization ability power competitive student in the world of work . Due to know a little from participant students who choose for direct work after graduating from agency school, then abilities possessed by participants educate when in the world of work be one indicator are also set by the school. The last indicator is increase participation and achievement student in various event race. This thing be marked with amount successful race won by SMAN 1 Purwantoro
- 2) Indicator character strong consist of 4 indicators. the first indicator could make it happen discipline participant educate. Second could make it happen ready as well as mind character lofty students. Third, there is an insight and level awareness student for conserve

environment the more growing. Final is insight and level awareness participant educate in attitude life nation and state the more growing .

- 3) Indicator insightful environment also includes 4 indicators. Indicator first could make it happen environment clean, cool, shady, and comfortable school. Indicator second is level awareness inhabitant school to preservation environment could increase. Indicator third is awareness whole residents at school to activity prevention damage environment could increase. Final is level concern inhabitant school to environment life could increase.
- 4) Component fourth is Which is the indicator of faith and taqwa from component this consist of three indicators. First is development knowledge and will student in perform worship according to their religion. The second indicator is realization tolerance religion in SMAN 1 Purwanto especially in Thing worship. The last indicator is development will student for to do goodness charity.

Related with achievement vision, SMAN 1 Purwanto apply TQM to improvement and development quality and quality service education in schools. Basically SMAN 1 Purwanto confess that condition of SMAN 1 Purwanto at this time is better than years previously however still need various repairs and upgrades standard quality if want to have power high competence compared with other equal schools.

Vice President field curriculum mention that curriculum is one very possessive thing role in determine quality system education at the same time Becomes guidelines in implementation teaching to all level education (Jusman, 2022). Implementation curriculum at SMAN 1 Purwanto besides based curriculum that has been determined by the Ministry of Education is also carried out various improvisation in its implementation. All learning in SMAN 1 Purwanto strive for for Becomes student-centered learning or activity study participant centred teaching educate with weigh willingness, interest, and talent from participant educate. A number of necessary things noticed related implementation curriculum education at SMAN 1 Purwanto is existence repair Keep going continuously and continuously on implementation curriculum so that there synchronization Among standard curriculum that has been set by the government with vision mission school and interests, talents, and abilities participant educate. Party the school also determines standard quality and standard a must service obeyed by all element school especially by parties' part service and parts education. Based on the narrative administrative officer explained that administrative officer required for doing standard operation service in every activity services performed. This thing It is intended that the services provided could give level satisfaction in accordance with needs and interests participant educate.

In accordance with which TQM concept is one of them is with To do development source power The people of SMAN 1 Purwanto also carry out resource reform power human started from enhancement capacity employee service and improvement capacity educator. Based on the narrative from the teacher who became resource person on research this is known that party school has carried out several times related training and coaching with TQM implementation and improvement capacity of human resources. The school party is also very concerned

attitudes and skills possessed by every teacher in skeleton ensure that participant educate could get level real education in accordance with demands of the times and development knowledge knowledge and technology. This Statement was also agreed by the participants educate who also becomes resource person on research this.

Participants educate mention that SMAN 1 Purwantoro really gives support and appreciation for each capable achievement achieved by participants educate. Party school is always striving for facilitate every need participant educate although on some Thing sometimes not yet could give maximum facilities. Several neither activity could facilitate because already be outside _ authority party school or capacity school no adequate for provide facility that. However, basically school always strive for give support and make the best facilities for development knowledge, insight, skills, and interests talent participant educate.

SMAN 1 Purwantoro is already here project self-going to digital school. This thing proven with start formulation education and teaching online based like informative and easy school web embodiment accessible, online learning portals (e-learning), as well as various online media that support embodiment digital school. SMAN 1 Purwantoro is one of the schools used as pilot svhool in digital school reform in the Province Central Java. because of that, various activities and activities related Thing the done by school cooperate with BPTIK Central Java. SMAN 1 Purwantoro is also very open with various participants' social media activities educate like making podcasts, and other online promotional video content.

The achievements at SMAN 1 Purwantoro are also varied. Not only originated from the student, a number of achievement is also achievements from educator. A number of the achievements of the participants studied at SMAN 1 Purwantoro is championship pencak silat on National Sports Day, Championships in events Young Scientist Competition at level national with achievements up to 13 championships won, championships at the olympics mathematics national, championship in scouting, and others. Educators at SMAN 1 Purwantoro have also won several times championship at the national teacher olympiad. Head SMAN 1 Purwantoro School even crowned as head school accomplished in 2018 and was crowned as head school dedicated, innovative and inspiring so that deliver he in get position as Head of Department of Education and Culture Province Central Java in January 2022. SMAN 1 Purwantoro was also crowned as school literacy level national. By general achievements achieved by participants educate nor educator at SMAN 1 Purwantoro consist of achievements in the fields of science, sports, arts, scouting, and works scientific.

Various achievements could not release from role application of TQM in management enhancement quality in SMAN 1 Purwantoro. Based on the concept of TQM, the application of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwantoro in skeleton increase quality service could see from a few integrated things with draft that. TQM at SMAN 1 Purwantoro based on TQM concept is as following:

- 1) All form learning and services at SMAN 1 Purwantoro use orientation student center which means participant educate as customer is focus from enhancement the quality and service provided by SMAN 1 Purwantoro.

- 2) Good process improvement service process or the education and teaching process at SMAN 1 Purwatoro always held with careful and systematic. Repair always conducted with clear concept and flow so that could obtain standard operational that can made guidelines.
- 3) All form repairs and upgrades quality service at SMAN 1 Purwanto based on vision and mission school so that effort repairs made is contain thinking period long because achievement vision and mission no could conduct in period short. Vision and mission contain ambition sublime that only could achieved over a long period of time and with effort Keep going continuously. because of that, SMAN 1 Purwatoro who carried out repair quality service based on TQM of course have element thinking period long
- 4) Repair source power man implemented on all inhabitant school without except. On employees' service, implemented enhancement capacity employee through training as well as coaching. Enhancement quality educators also do in skeleton give service excellent and appropriate education with demands of the times. Enhancement ability participant teaching is also done through various support and giving facilities on various field the interests and talents of each participant educate. SMAN 1 Purwatoro have at least 4 extracurricular which can be a medium for participant educate for develop abilities and skills possessed. Extracurricular the consist of Scouts, ROHIS, Youth Red Cross (PMR), and Sports.
- 5) Commitment all element organization for guard quality service could see from spirit whole element school start from the authorities for make policies, employees services, educators, and participants compact learner for could reach level best that can be achieved by SMAN 1 Purwatoro. Based on results observation and interview could see that between elements in school each other support one each other. Statements given by each party to each other related and supportive as well as no there is statement which nature opposite or no appropriate.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been done could concluded that application Total Quality Management (TQM) at SMAN 1 Purwatoro could bring good impact for school. The application of TQM grows spirit whole inhabitant school for optimizing the potential of the school. Application of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwatoro target whole inhabitant school with focus main is participant educate. Result of implementation of TQM in the end not only felt by participants educate however felt by all inhabitant school as well as all related parties with school. The existence of TQM makes services at school Becomes better. Enhancement service this could feel good at service administration or service education.

The implementation of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwatoro has also in accordance with which TQM concepts exist several criteria like focus to customers, systematic process improvement, containing thinking expect long, exist repair source power humans, and existence commitment from whole related parties. Because of it can concluded that implementation of TQM at SMAN 1 Purwatoro already good and appropriate the concept. Then, no amazed if the results obtained are also sufficient satisfactory.

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